

SECTION OF BIOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL SCIENCES

METHODS FOR CORRECTING THE SHAPE AND SIZE OF THE UPPER JAW INCISORS

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Abstract

The abnormally low clinical height of the crowns of the frontal group of teeth (microdentia) of the upper jaw is a rather difficult problem in achieving the aesthetic result of prosthetics. Restoring the original shape of the destroyed coronal part of such teeth with metal-ceramic crowns or veneers, as a rule, does not give the desired cosmetic treatment result. This is due to the fact that it is not realistic to recreate normal crown sizes without surgical correction of the gingival margin.

Keywords: microdentia of the anterior teeth of the upper jaw, surgical and orthopedic correction.

Correction of the size of the crowns of the frontal group of teeth in most cases can be done using gingivectomy, since their insufficient height from a cosmetic point of view is usually due to an excessively wide area of the attached gum [3]. However, in some cases, when the width of the attached gum zone is 2–3 mm, gingivectomy is contraindicated, and surgical correction of the size of the teeth must be performed using apically displaced mucoperiosteal flaps [2, 3]. The above can be demonstrated using the following clinical example: Patient E., 21 years old. Diagnosis: chronic periodontitis of 11 and 21 teeth. Prosthetics were performed 1 year ago (metal-ceramic crowns were made for teeth 11 and 21). Dissatisfied with the cosmetic result. Clinically: teeth 11 and 21 under metal-ceramic crowns. The height of the teeth is disproportionately small. The ratio of the width of the crowns to their height is 1:1, and the normal ratio in women is 0.8 (1). The width of the attached gum zone is 3–3.5 mm. There is a diastema 2.5 mm wide and a low attachment of the frenulum of the upper lip. In the area of the projection of the root of the 11th tooth there is a fistula, there is no separation, the mobility of the 11th tooth is grade I. There is no mobility of the 21st tooth. X-ray: there are 11 and 21 tabs in the roots, the canals are sealed up to the tops. In the area of the lower 1/3 of the root of the 11th tooth there is a small (0.5 x 1.0 mm) focus of bone tissue resorption. The patient's wishes: replace the crowns of teeth 11 and 21, while eliminating the diastema, giving teeth 11 and 21 a natural shape and size. Treatment plan: 1) computer simulation of changes in the shape and size of teeth, coordination of these changes with the patient; 2) surgical correction of the height of the gingival margin using an apically displaced mucoperiosteal flap, revision of the fistula and source of inflammation in the area of the 11th tooth; 3) production of temporary plastic crowns for fixation and formation of a new level of the gingival margin; 4) production of metal-ceramic crowns for 11 and 21 teeth. Progress of treatment: After

agreeing with the patient on the treatment plan and the new sizes of the crowns of teeth 11 and 21, an operation was performed to surgically correct the height of the gingival margin. Under infiltration anesthesia, an incision was made and a trapezoidal mucoperiosteal flap was formed. It was discovered that part of the root of the 11th tooth was exposed (the vestibular wall of the alveolus was missing for 1/4 of the length of the root) and a crack in the root of this tooth. This circumstance made adjustments to the course of the operation. In addition to the revision of the tissues surrounding the root of the 11th tooth, a "weakening" hole was drilled in the root in the upper part of the crack, filling of the crack and hole, grinding and polishing of the root surface and reconstruction of the vestibular wall of its socket using a block of xenohydroxyapatite (the drug "Biomatrix") and enriched with platelets and fibrin gel from the patient's autologous blood. After reconstruction of the vestibular wall of the alveolus of the 11th tooth and displacement of the mucoperiosteal flap to a given height, it was fixed using sutures and a "bandage" of photopolymer applied to the area of lengthening of the crowns of teeth 11 and 21. A crack in the root of the 11th tooth, discovered during the operation, made adjustments not only to the course of the operation, but also to the subsequent prosthetic plan. It was decided to make not single crowns, as previously assumed, but a bridge-like prosthesis for 11 and 21 teeth for splinting the supporting teeth. 2 weeks after the operation, a temporary plastic prosthesis was made supporting teeth 11 and 21, which the patient used for 2 months. 2 months after the operation, the temporary acrylic crowns were removed and the condition of the supporting teeth and surrounding tissues was examined. No tooth mobility was observed. The gingival margin at the new level was completely formed. No signs of inflammation were detected. Metal-ceramic prosthetic crowns were made with fixation on teeth 11 and 21.

Despite the change in prosthetic treatment tactics (instead of single crowns, a bridge had to be made to splint teeth 11 and 21), it was possible to achieve a cosmetic result that was completely satisfactory to the patient. Conclusions: — Surgical correction of the height of the gingival margin using apically displaced mucoperiosteal flaps makes it possible to give an adequate shape to the coronal part of the teeth for cosmetic purposes and achieve a good cosmetic result of prosthetics or restoration using veneers. — The use of the technique of apical (as well as coronal) displacement of mucoperiosteal flaps allows you to change the size of the crowns of the frontal group of teeth, bringing their height and proportions to an adequate ratio with the shape of the face, dental arch, shape and size of neighboring teeth. — During surgical, as well as orthopedic, correction of the shape of teeth, it is necessary to use methods of imitation (visualization) of the planned and desired cosmetic result. Such visualization of the results can be done by computer reconstruction using

photographs of the original clinical situation or by making temporary crowns or veneers. — As a primary guideline for determining the virtually correct form of teeth from a cosmetic point of view, it is quite convenient to use the J.L. classification. Williams (correlation of the shape of the teeth with the oval of the face and the curvature of the dental arch), and to calculate the size of the teeth - categories of harmonization of the shape and size of the teeth according to G.W. Clapp [1,4].

References

1. Dmitrienko, S.V., Krajushkin A.I., Sapin M.R. *Anatomija zubov cheloveka*. — M.: «Medicinskaja kniga», 2000. — 193 s.
2. Shish Zh., Aoshima H. *Anatomija ulybki*. — M.: «Azbuka», 2005. — 109 s.
3. Bensimon G. // *Int. Journal of Periodontics & Restorative Dent.* — 1999. — V.19, N4. — C. 333 – 341.
4. Sellen Ph., Jagger D., Harrison A. // *Int. Journal of Prosthodont.* — 1999. — V.12, N1. — C. 51 – 58.